

PSYCHOLINGUISTICS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION IS THE ISSUE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT PRACTICE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10663124>

As soon as a person is born, he feels the need for speech communication. From the first days of his life, the baby begins to perceive communication in the speech process through his senses. However, the child does not know how to use the norms of the language, he does not yet fully understand the process of socialization, so he makes speech mistakes. Russian linguist T. G. Paymurzina says that ineffective communication is called communicative error and communicative failure in science. Communicative failure refers to the negative outcome of communication, failure of the speaker to achieve his goal, unplanned negative emotions, and confrontational behavior. Therefore, a communicative error is a defective treatment or ambiguity.

Communicative obstacles in the expression of thought, in the process of speech communication, are clearly manifested mainly in the speech of preschool children. According to the results of a series of observations, the speech of preschool children is divided into the following types.

1. A one-year-old and three-month-old boy addressed his brother for the first time through the sound "a". Although the child of this age has heard the lexeme "brother" several times in the process of communication, he preferred to use the method that has become a habit in his psychology. This speech expression, used in relation to a close relative, causes misunderstanding in people who meet the child for the first time, who start communicating with him for the first time. The child did not intend to use the one-sound form of address, he used the sound "a" because it was easy for him to pronounce. Later, even though the boy could pronounce the word "brother", he used to refer to his brother with the sound "a".

2. A two-year-old and one-month-old boy pronounced the word "blessing" in a pleading tone in his speech. In the process of communication, the child did not use any gestures or movements. This situation caused trouble for those around him, that is, those around him did not understand what the child wanted. A two-year-old and one-month-old boy pronounced the word "blessing" in a pleading tone in his speech. In the process of communication, the child did not use any gestures or movements. This situation caused trouble for those around him, that is, those around him did not understand what the child wanted.

3. In the speech of a four-year-old and three-month-old child, it can be observed that the word "disk" is pronounced in the style of "dicks". A child of this age can pronounce one of the consecutive consonants in a word without omitting it. However, the difficulty in pronunciation leads to a violation of the sequence in the child's speech. Children of this age should be required to show what they want to say not only through gestures or actions, but also to explain it through speech.

4. The lexeme "biy naysa beyin" (give something) was used in the speech of a three-year-old and seven-month-old child. Often, adults want to tease or distract a child and say "I'll give you something" and mean some kind of candy, for example, chocolate. As a result, if the child misses sweets, he will continue to appeal in the same way.

5. In the speech of a three-year-old and seven-month-old child in the form of "I'm not getting enough", there is an imbalance of form and content. In the dialect of the city of Tashkent, the phrase "emagim kemayapti" means exactly "emigim kemayapti". The boy wanted to say that he did not want to eat. The defect in the child's speech is that he made a communicative error by using the inflectional affix "ma" twice, which prevented his speech from being understood. Sometimes in children's speech, cases of using speech units with emphasis on sound are also observed. For example, the child gets used to pronouncing the sound coming from his father's car in the form of "ginna" in his speech, or to pronounce it in the form of "dit-dit", "pap-pap" after hearing the car's signal. Later, even if he sees other cars, he will pronounce the same sounds. Even his father starts pointing like this.

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